

THE IMPACT OF THE SITUATION ON THE LABOR MARKET ON MIGRATION PROCESSES

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Annotation. This article describes the situation in the labor market and its impact on migration processes.

Keywords: population, labor market, unemployment, jobs, labor migration, migration processes, migration policy, regulation of labor migration.

The creation of a modern and active structure of the labor market in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the regulation of labor migration processes is one of the important tasks of economic reforms. The solution of this most important task will create the basis for the development of enterprises and the network economy in the regions and, ultimately, economic growth.

Rapid population growth is one of the characteristics of Uzbekistan. According to statistical data, the highest ever rate of population growth in the republic corresponds to the present stage: the average annual population growth is 3-3.5%. Over the next thirty years, the population of Uzbekistan increased by almost 12 million people, and over the previous thirty-year period, it increased by only 3.5 million people.

The country's population growth rate is consistently outpacing the growth rate of other regions, which is clearly manifested in the fact that the share of the Republic of Uzbekistan is steadily increasing in the total population of the CIS countries. For example, if in 1926 a little more than three percent of the population of the CIS countries lived in Uzbekistan, now this figure is more than seven percent.

The population of the republic is unevenly distributed among the regions, therefore, in terms of average population density, Uzbekistan is the leader among the CIS countries and the republics of Central Asia.

According to the UN Population Fund, Uzbekistan ranks 40th among countries in terms of population, accounting for 0.44% of the world's population.¹

Due to the rapid growth of the population, the average population density per square kilometer of the territory of the republic as of January 1, 2022 was 78.6 people². This figure increased by 1.6 people compared to 2021. (In 2021, there were 77.0 people per 1 km²). An increase in population means that there will be changes in the labor force.

Table 1.

¹ UN reports. *The largest countries in the world by population in 2021.* <https://top-rf.ru/516-reyting-stran>.

² *Information of the State Committee on Statistics of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The demographic situation of the Republic of Uzbekistan for January-December 2021.*

Dynamics of the composition of labor resources in the Republic of Uzbekistan, million people.

Indicators	Years					
	2010	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Resident population, total	29,1	32,1	32,6	33,3	33,9	34,6
including;						
urban population, %	51,2	50,6	50,6	50,5	50,6	50,7
rural population, %	48,8	49,4	49,4	49,5	49,4	49,3
Labor resources, total	16,7	18,7	18,8	19,0	19,2	19,3
including;						
in the town, %	54,6	53,3	53,3	53,1	54,7	54,8
In the village, %	45,4	46,7	46,7	46,9	45,3	45,2
Economically active population, total	12,3	14,4	14,6	14,9	14,8	15,0
including;						
in the town, %	55,7	52,1	52,5	52,7	55,3	56,1
In the village, %	44,3	47,9	47,5	47,3	44,7	43,9

Source: Calculated based on data from the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics.

Typically, the need for jobs is the supply of labor. In our republic, there is a big difference between the demand for labor force and the supply of labor force. This causes tension in the labor market.

Despite the systemic measures taken to ensure employment in our republic, the number and level of unemployment is increasing.

The analyzes carried out showed that the economically active population is growing at a faster pace than the working-age population, the level of economic activity of the population increased from 73.4 percent in 2010 to 77.4 percent in 2021, that is, by 4 points. It can be seen that the employment rate of the population increased to 69.2%, and since the beginning of the pandemic it has decreased to 66.0%.

Table 2.

Dynamics of the main indicators of the labor market of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Indicators	Years						Differences 2021/ 2010, %
	2010	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	
Number of labor resources, thousand people	16726,0	18666,3	18829,6	18949,0	19158,2	19345,0	115,6
Economically active population, thousand people	12286,6	14357,3	14641,7	14876,4	14797,4	14980,7	121,9
The level of economic activity of the population, in %	73,4	76,9	77,7	78,5	77,2	77,4	X
Employment rate, in %	66,9	69,2	67,4	68,1	66,0	66,9	X
Number of unemployed, thousand people	658,2	837,0	1368,6	1335,3	1561,0	1441,9	219,0
Unemployment rate, in %	5,4	5,8	9,3	9,0	10,5	9,6	X

Source: Calculated based on data from the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

During the study period, the number of unemployed increased almost 2.2 times, the unemployment rate increased from 5.4 percent to 9.6 percent. The unemployment rate in Uzbekistan began to grow in 2018 (9.3%). It can be seen that over the analyzed period, this indicator increased to 10.6 percent. The analysis showed that the growth rate of the economically active population is 121.9 percent, of which 66.9 percent are employed.

The analysis shows the complexity of the situation in the labor market. Data analysis showed that the lack of jobs, low wages and low self-employment opportunities in rural areas are the reasons for the increase in migration flows. According to sources, the number of labor resources in Uzbekistan in 2020 will be 19.1 million people, of which 1.678 million foreign labor migrants accounted for 8.8% of the working population.³

³ *Economic situation in Uzbekistan. Labor migration from Uzbekistan to the Russian Federation: trends, problems and opportunities. Institute for Research and Expertise. M.: 2022*

Table 3.

Labor force and migration indicators in Uzbekistan (2020).

Source: Economic situation in Uzbekistan. Labor migration from Uzbekistan to the Russian Federation: trends, problems and opportunities. Institute for Research and Expertise. M.: 2022

In 2021, 8.6 percent of foreign labor migrants were in the working-age population. Over the past year, this figure has decreased by 0.2 points. Of course, this means that there is a positive trend.

However, the fact that not all the unemployed will be able to find work will increase the scale of migration.

Name of regions	Number (thousand people)				Share of people working abroad (%)		
	working abroad	labor resources	economically active population	employment in the economy	labor resources	economically active population	employment in the economy
The Republic of Uzbekistan	1678	19142	14797,9	13240	8,8	11,3	12,7
Republic of Karakalpakstan	126,3	1069	781,7	699,3	11,8	16,2	18,1
areas:							
Samarkand	234,5	2130,4	1585,4	1410,9	11,0	14,8	16,6
Andijan	228,7	1752,9	1387,3	1236,7	13,0	16,5	18,5
Fergana	197,7	2068,5	1613,9	1438,3	9,6	12,2	13,7
Tashkent	143,7	1614,9	1336,5	1195,6	8,9	10,8	12,0
Khorezm	139,9	1042,4	800,8	713,7	13,4	17,5	19,6
Kashkadarya	131,0	1817,6	1334,2	1186,7	7,2	9,8	11,0
Surkhandarya	112,5	1457,6	1104,1	982,0	7,7	10,2	11,5
Bukhara	77,6	1070,4	876,7	783,6	7,2	8,9	9,9
Namangan	63,3	1579,5	1205,3	1078,0	4,0	5,3	5,9
Syrdarya	45,6	485,7	375,1	333,7	9,4	12,2	13,7
Jizzakh	39,9	774,6	598,9	533,1	5,2	6,7	7,5
Navoi	23,1	556,3	446,2	404,3	4,2	5,2	5,7
Tashkent city	114,5	1722,3	1351,8	1243,7	6,6	8,5	9,2

Figure 1. Reasons for non-employment in the labor market, %.

Source: Calculated based on data from the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

An analysis of labor migration by regions shows that most of those who left the republic went to work in the Russian Federation, and in the regions they indicate that (96.4%) of those working in this region were from Bukhara, (95.2%) from Kashkadarya, (92.9%) from Syrdarya, (87.8%) from Fergana regions. Due to the proximity of Kazakhstan to the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 72.9% were those leaving this region. Those who left to work in Turkey amounted to 15.2% from Tashkent, 13.6% from Namangan and 12.7% from Andijan regions.

Today, most of the migrants who go abroad to work are in Kazakhstan and the Russian Federation. This fact is due to the fact that it is easier to get there. Given that the majority of our citizens in both countries work primarily in the construction industry, women in these countries face a number of challenges.⁴

It can be seen that labor migrants work abroad in various fields. Sectoral and gender analysis of foreign labor activity showed that men have higher employment opportunities than women. The fact that 36.6% of men worked in small enterprises, 22.2% in large enterprises, and 21.6% in private enterprises is a clear proof of our above opinion. In general, 25.6 percent of women worked in light industry, and 21.3 percent worked as cooks, nannies and family nurses.

Labor migration plays an important role in solving the problem of employment in the conditions of stable growth of labor resources and labor surplus in the labor market of Uzbekistan. This reduces the demographic pressure on local labor markets, especially in densely populated areas, and is in fact an alternative to unemployment. Given the scale of external labor migration,

⁴ Abdurakhmanov G.Kh., Islamova V.V. Economic and demographic aspects of external migration of Uzbekistan. Moscow Economic Journal. 2022. № 5. URL: <https://qje.su/economicheskaya-teoriya/moskovskij-economicheskij-zhurnal-5-2022-11>

it is currently becoming one of the most important segments of the labor market in Uzbekistan - the segment of external employment.⁵

At the same time, we believe that an excessive increase in external labor migration will have negative consequences. The labor market of Uzbekistan is losing its most active and able-bodied population. Despite the state's efforts to expand organized external labor migration, most Uzbeks find work on their own, often irretrievably losing professional knowledge and skills outside their profession and specialization. At the same time, the shortage of specialists in the national labor market is increasing, and problems arise in providing industrial enterprises with personnel.

It should be noted that labor migration occurs against the background of the general migration flow from the republic. Taken together, this already creates problems with a skilled workforce. The growing number of qualified personnel, the insufficient use of the professional and professional potential of thousands of people is already hindering the development of the country. Moreover, migrant workers who work illegally do not have social protection either from their own country or from the host country.⁶

The conducted studies show that labor migration complements the state's ability to regulate the labor market.

The critical situation in the labor market of the republic requires further activation of a certain targeted policy in relation to employment.

In densely populated areas of the republic, this problem is especially acute, creating more favorable conditions for creating new jobs in the regions, developing industry, effectively using various forms of labor activity, developing the household, small business and private entrepreneurship, as well as the activities of farms in rural areas, creates the basis for providing employment to the population and increasing its income.

We will continue our opinion with information about the jobs created in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Table 4.

The structure of employment in the sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan, %

Indicators	Years						
	2010	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2021/ 2010., + : -;
Employed population, total	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	-

⁵ Abdurakhmanov K.Kh., Mukhitdinov E.M., Grishin V.I. Labor migration and supply chain assessment in the labor market // *Journal of International Supply Chain Management. IJSCM*, ISSN: 2050-7399 (online), ExcelingTech Pub, UK. (<http://excelingtech.co.uk/>), volume 8, April 2, 2019.

⁶ *Global Migration Database. International Fund for Migrants 2020: International Organization for Migration (IOM)*

In particular, by type of economic activity							
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	26,8	27,2	26,6	26,2	26,4	25,9	- 0,9
Industry	13,8	13,5	13,6	13,5	13,7	13,9	0,1
Construction	8,9	9,5	9,1	9,8	9,9	9,5	0,6
Trade	10,6	10,9	10,6	10,6	10,6	11,4	0,7
Delivery and storage	4,4	4,8	4,9	4,8	4,6	4,8	0,4
Education	9,5	8,2	8,4	8,4	8,8	8,7	- 0,8
Health and social services	5,1	4,5	4,6	4,6	5,1	4,9	-0,3
Other areas of activity	20,9	21,4	22,3	22,3	21,0	21,0	0,1

Source: Calculated based on data from the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Data analysis shows that the bulk of the labor force is employed in construction, transportation and storage, agriculture and forestry. There is a decrease in the employed population in agriculture, forestry and fisheries from 26.9% to 25.9%. Despite this trend, the majority of the employed population belongs to these three sectors of the economy. At the same time, there is a downward trend in employment in some industries. In particular, during the study period, it can be seen that the employment of labor resources in education (0.8%), healthcare and social services (0.2%). This situation is observed as a result of reforms related to the structural change in the economy of our republic in the analyzed years.

Comprehensive support for entrepreneurship in our country, solving on this basis the tasks of increasing employment and welfare of the population is one of the main directions of socio-economic policy. "...we can only make progress and a prosperous life through active enterprise, tireless work and aspiration".⁷

As you know, one of the opportunities for small businesses and private businesses, which is of strategic importance for the economy of the country, especially the region, is employment and the creation of new jobs. This creates ample opportunities for small businesses and private entrepreneurship to provide employment for the population of the republic. In this area, 73.8% of the population employed in the economy in 2020 corresponded to the share of small business and private entrepreneurship. Their share in the country's GDP this year amounted to 53.9 percent.⁸

⁷Mirziyoev Sh.M. *Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis // People's Word, December 29, 2018*

⁸Calculated by the author. *Information of the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on statistics for 2021.*

Therefore, it can be concluded from the data that due to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, not only economic growth in the regions is achieved, but also the possibility of solving existing social problems.

An analysis of these statistical indicators indicates that the government of our republic is opening a wide path for small business and private entrepreneurship, in connection with which economic reforms are being consistently implemented aimed at increasing employment.

The achievement of such a result is, first of all, proof that the socio-economic reforms being carried out in our country are aimed at improving the living standards and welfare of the population.

The development of entrepreneurship creates the basis for the formation of a class of small owners, who are considered the main driving force of the market economy, to create an opportunity to enrich the market of our country with consumer goods and various services, increase the income of each family and solve the problem of unemployment in exchange for creating new jobs. Thanks to the rational economic policy pursued in the country, such effective forms of employment as home, family business and crafts have been developed, which contribute to the manifestation of entrepreneurial abilities and creative labor potential of the population. The sources of financing for the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship are the local budget, funds from the Employment Support Fund and personal funds of private entrepreneurs.⁹

In our opinion, the most important of the economic measures to increase the demand for labor is the implementation of structural changes in the sectors of the economy. This is achieved primarily through the development of forms of ownership, the creation of new jobs, the rational use of working time, increasing the material and moral interest of workers, and the rational establishment of taxes.

Among the important economic measures are the creation of new jobs in the manufacturing industry and the service sector, the provision of soft loans by the state to expand production, and the introduction of advanced technologies. These activities involve the least investment in creating additional jobs and play an important role in increasing the demand for labor.¹⁰

Based on the foregoing, we can say that in the development of relations between the CIS countries, in the regulation of labor migration, taking into account national interests, it is advisable to pay attention to the implementation of such measures as the coordination of relevant decisions and the prevention of illegal migration.

In our country, there are many employment opportunities for migrants who have returned from abroad. In our opinion, the opportunities for the development of small business, private entrepreneurship, the service sector and the processing industry in this regard are as follows:

⁹ *Israilova D.K. Social and General Aspects of Labor Export// Colloquium-Journal Polish Journal of International Scientific Publications. - Warsaw, 2020. Issue 3 No. 33 (85), pp. 27-30.*

¹⁰ *Israilova D.K. Regulation of labor migration in Uzbekistan: theory and practice. MONOGRAPH. - T.: Publishing house of TDIU "IKTISODILOT", 2022. - 240 p.*

1. Organization of free training seminars on business consultations (accounting, finance, taxes, marketing, information technology) for those who are engaged in entrepreneurship and have a desire to do it;

2. The expansion and emergence of new types of needs, the release of labor force from the sphere of production create conditions for the flow of this labor force into the service sector.

3. Creation of a comprehensively developed industry of recreation and hotel services for tourists vacationing in sanatoriums, holiday homes and boarding houses; This will create additional jobs.

The implementation of the above measures will make it possible to remove the tense situation in the labor market and thereby regulate migration processes.